

(Table 2) for the system (chlorobenzene + benzene) is a linear function of $f_1 f_2$ and passes through the origin. This suggests that the charge transfer type complexes are formed between chlorobenzene and benzene.

Fig. 1. Chlorobenzene in benzene.

It is worth mentioning here that for practical purposes a careful application of the equations¹ is desirable.

TABLE 2—CHLOROBENZENE IN BENZENE

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
$f_1 f_2$	Solution Polarisation P_{12}	Total Polarisation of the solution $P_{12} = P_1 F_1 + P_2 F_2$	Excess Polarisation PE (2)-(3)
0.0204	27.687	27.394	+0.293
0.0300	28.191	27.764	+0.427
0.0390	28.663	28.113	+0.550
0.0481	29.167	28.479	+0.688
0.0552	29.635	28.765	+0.870
0.0633	30.029	29.104	+0.925

ϵ_1 (dielectric constant of solvent) = 2.2617
 ϵ_2 (dielectric constant of solute) = 5.7407
 d_1 (density of solvent) = 0.8679 g/ml.
 d_2 (density of solute) = 1.0955 g/ml.

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Transport Processes and Some New Symmetries

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IN continuation to our earlier communication¹, we now report on the occurrence of some new symmetries, about which only a scanty information is available in the literature^{2,3} and that too without any systematic elaboration.

If J'_1, J'_2, \dots, J'_r be the independent linear combinations of some original flows J_1, J_2, \dots, J_r each of which is represented as

$$J_i = \left(\frac{\partial J_i}{\partial X_i} \right)_0 X_i + \frac{1}{2!} \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_i}{\partial X_i^2} \right)_0 X_i^2 + \frac{1}{3!} \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_i}{\partial X_i^3} \right)_0 X_i^3 + \dots \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, r) \quad \dots (1)$$

and likewise their corresponding conjugate forces X'_1, X'_2, \dots, X'_r be the linear combinations of the original forces X_1, X_2, \dots, X_r as given under

$$\begin{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} J'_1 \\ J'_2 \\ \vdots \\ J'_r \end{bmatrix} \\ F \end{matrix} = \begin{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{11} & n_{12} & \dots & n_{1r} \\ n_{21} & n_{22} & \dots & n_{2r} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ n_{r1} & n_{r2} & \dots & n_{rr} \end{bmatrix} \\ N \end{matrix} \begin{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} J_1 \\ J_2 \\ \dots \\ J_r \end{bmatrix} \\ J \end{matrix} \quad \text{and} \\ \begin{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} X'_1 \\ X'_2 \\ \dots \\ X'_r \end{bmatrix} \\ Y \end{matrix} = \begin{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1r} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2r} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{r1} & a_{r2} & \dots & a_{rr} \end{bmatrix} \\ A \end{matrix} \begin{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_1 \\ X_2 \\ \dots \\ X_r \end{bmatrix} \\ X \end{matrix} \quad \dots (2)$$

the n th order coefficient^{1,4,5} L_n is obtained as

$$L_n = \left(\begin{matrix} n_1 & n_2 & \dots & n_r \\ n_{11} & n_{21} & \dots & n_{r1} \end{matrix} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^n J_1}{\partial X_1^n} \right)_0 + \left(\begin{matrix} n_1 & n_2 & \dots & n_r \\ n_{12} & n_{22} & \dots & n_{r2} \end{matrix} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^n J_2}{\partial X_2^n} \right)_0 + \dots + \left(\begin{matrix} n_1 & n_2 & \dots & n_r \\ n_{1r} & n_{2r} & \dots & n_{rr} \end{matrix} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^n J_r}{\partial X_r^n} \right)_0 \quad \dots (3)$$

where $\sum_{k=1}^r n_k = n+1$.

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Eq. (3) indicates that Li's n th order coefficients, L_n will be symmetrical among themselves, provided, the combination of the integers involved in their subscripts remains unaltered. On elaborate analysis of this eq. it appears, however, that even a change in combination of the integers associated with L_n 's may be allowed without changing their value. The new symmetries thus obtained, may be called special symmetries, the realisation of which may be visualised under the following circumstances :

(A) If all the elements n_{ij} ($i = j = 1, 2, \dots, r$) in the matrix of transformation N in eq. (2) be equal to 'b' or b_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, r$) and atleast one of which in each of all columns or all but one column be associated with a negative sign, e.g., the p th element of 1st column, q th of the 2nd column ... sth of the i th column ... and 1st of the r th column forming linearly independent combinations then L_n will be given by

$$L_n = (-1)^{n_p} b^{n+1} \left(\frac{\partial^n J_1}{\partial X_1^n} \right)_0 + (-1)^{n_q} b^{n+1} \left(\frac{\partial^n J_2}{\partial X_2^n} \right)_0$$

$$+ \dots + (-1)^{n_s} b^{n+1} \left(\frac{\partial^n J_i}{\partial X_i^n} \right)_0$$

$$+ \dots + (-1)^{n_r} b^{n+1} \left(\frac{\partial^n J_r}{\partial X_r^n} \right)_0 \quad \dots (4)$$

$$L_n = (-1)^{n_p} b_1^{n+1} \left(\frac{\partial^n J_1}{\partial X_1^n} \right)_0 + (-1)^{n_q} b_2^{n+1} \left(\frac{\partial^n J_2}{\partial X_2^n} \right)_0$$

$$+ \dots + (-1)^{n_s} b_i^{n+1} \left(\frac{\partial^n J_i}{\partial X_i^n} \right)_0$$

$$+ \dots + (-1)^{n_r} b_r^{n+1} \left(\frac{\partial^n J_r}{\partial X_r^n} \right)_0 \quad \dots (5)$$

From eqs. (4) and (5) it is evident that L_n will be symmetrical with the only proviso that the odd and the even character of the respective n_k 's remains unimpaired. Thus, even if the s th element of the i th column, say, is not associated with a negative sign and the i th term is positive for all values of n_s the condition of special symmetry relation will remain unaffected on account of the fact that odd or even character of n_s can not be changed without having a subsequent change in the characters of other n_k 's. However, in this case symmetry relation (6), to be described later will not hold.

In case each column contains more than one element associated with a negative sign there would be no substantial change in the expression of L_n as given in eqs. (4) and (5) except that in place of n_k 's there would be Σ_p 's as the power of (-1) , where Σ_p indicates that sum of those n_k 's which are related to the negatively signed elements in the p th term ($p = 1, 2, \dots, r$). Hence special symmetry relation will be observed only when the odd and even character of Σ_p is maintained in each and every term.

One more symmetry relation, which follows from the above equations, will be given by

$$L_n \text{ (with odd and even } n_k \text{'s or } \Sigma_p \text{'s)}$$

$$= -L_n \text{ (with odd and even character of } n_k \text{'s or } \Sigma_p \text{'s reversed)} \quad \dots (6)$$

The examples given below will illustrate the symmetry relations discussed above.

(i) When some n_k 's are odd and some are even

$$L_{1112233444} = L_{1112222444} = -L_{1122233344} = -L_{111123333}$$

$n_1 = 3,$	$n_1 = 3,$	$n_1 = 2,$	$n_1 = 4,$
$n_2 = 2,$	$n_2 = 4,$	$n_2 = 3,$	$n_2 = 1,$
$n_3 = 2,$	$n_3 = 0,$	$n_3 = 3,$	$n_3 = 5,$
$n_4 = 3.$	$n_4 = 3.$	$n_4 = 2.$	$n_4 = 0.$

(ii) Let $\Sigma_1 = n_1 + n_2, \Sigma_2 = n_2 + n_3, \Sigma_3 = n_3 + n_4, \Sigma_4 = n_4 + n_1$, then

$$L_{1122233344} = L_{1112233444} = -L_{1112333344} = -L_{1112223344}$$

$\Sigma_1 = 5,$	$\Sigma_1 = 5,$	$\Sigma_1 = 4,$	$\Sigma_1 = 6,$
$\Sigma_2 = 6,$	$\Sigma_2 = 4,$	$\Sigma_2 = 5,$	$\Sigma_2 = 5,$
$\Sigma_3 = 5,$	$\Sigma_3 = 5,$	$\Sigma_3 = 6,$	$\Sigma_3 = 4,$
$\Sigma_4 = 4.$	$\Sigma_4 = 6.$	$\Sigma_4 = 5.$	$\Sigma_4 = 5.$

(B) One more transformation, as discussed under, needs exemplification to show the occurrence of special symmetries.

If the corresponding elements of each pair of any two rows, namely those of p th and q th row, s th row and v th row, etc. of the transformation matrix N , are reciprocals and the elements of the remaining lone row in the event of the number of rows in the matrix being odd, say, the i th row are (a) unity or (b) a constant, m or (c) all different, m_1, m_2, \dots, m_r then special symmetry relation will occur only when the numbers of integers corresponding to each such pair of rows are equal viz., $n_p = n_q, n_s = n_v$ etc. in the subscripts L_n . The expression for L_n is obtained as

$$L_n = \left(\frac{\partial^n J_1}{\partial X_1^n} \right)_0 + \left(\frac{\partial^n J_2}{\partial X_2^n} \right)_0 + \dots + \left(\frac{\partial^n J_r}{\partial X_r^n} \right)_0 \quad \dots (7)$$

when r is even, or r is odd and the elements of the lone row are unity as in (a). For (b) and (c) with odd value of r , L_n will be expressed as

$$L_n = m^{n_1} \left(\frac{\partial^n J_1}{\partial X_1^n} \right)_0 + m^{n_2} \left(\frac{\partial^n J_2}{\partial X_2^n} \right)_0 + \dots + m^{n_i} \left(\frac{\partial^n J_r}{\partial X_r^n} \right)_0 \quad \dots (8)$$

and

$$L_n = m_1 n_i \left(\frac{\partial^n J_1}{\partial X_1^n} \right)_0 + m_2 n_i \left(\frac{\partial^n J_2}{\partial X_2^n} \right)_0 + \dots + m_r n_i \left(\frac{\partial^n J_r}{\partial X_r^n} \right)_0 \dots (9)$$

respectively. Eqs. (8) and (9) suggest that such symmetries will depend on the constancy of n_i . The examples presented below will clarify the position further. Examples—

(a) When r is even ($r = 4$)

(Elements of rows 1 and 2, 3, and 4 being reciprocals)

$$L_{1112233344} = L_{1122233344} = L_{1222234444}$$

$$n_1 = 3, n_2 = 2 \quad n_1 = 2, n_2 = 3 \quad n_1 = 1, n_2 = 4$$

$$n_3 = 3, n_4 = 2 \quad n_3 = 2, n_4 = 3 \quad n_3 = 1, n_4 = 4$$

(b) When r is odd ($r = 5$) and elements of lone (5th) row are unity (Elements of rows 1 and 2, 3 and 4 being reciprocals)

$$L_{11122334455} = L_{1233445555} = L_{1111222234}$$

$$n_1 = 2, n_2 = 2 \quad n_1 = 1, n_2 = 1 \quad n_1 = 4, n_2 = 4$$

$$n_3 = 2, n_4 = 2 \quad n_3 = 2, n_4 = 2 \quad n_3 = 1, n_4 = 1$$

$$n_5 = 2. \quad n_5 = 4. \quad n_5 = 0.$$

(c) When r is odd and the elements of the lone (5th) row are a constant or different (Elements of rows 1, and 2, 3 and 4 being reciprocals)

$$L_{11122234455} = L_{1233344455} = L_{1111222255}$$

$$n_1 = 3, n_2 = 3 \quad n_1 = 1, n_2 = 1 \quad n_1 = 4, n_2 = 4$$

$$n_3 = 1, n_4 = 1 \quad n_3 = 3, n_4 = 3 \quad n_3 = 0, n_4 = 0$$

$$n_5 = 2. \quad n_5 = 2. \quad n_5 = 2.$$

The success and failure to observe the special symmetries to hold in some earlier communication³ thus gets explained on the basis of this generalised discussion.

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Microdetermination of 3-methyl-3-(3',5'-dibromo-2', 4'-dihydroxyphenyl) tetrachlorophthalide using ceric sulphate as oxidising agent

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THE dye (I) has been reported in literature by Singh and Gupta¹, and has been shown to be useful as an adsorption indicator² by the same authors.

In the present communication the authors have described quantitative determination of (I) in micro amounts using Ceric sulphate as an oxidising agent in presence of a large excess of acid. Since acetic acid is one of the main oxidation products requiring 50 equivalence, probably the following reaction takes place

In the reaction of the dye (I) acetic acid was isolated and identified as mentioned in the discussion.

Experimental

Reagents used : Dye (I) prepared from *o*-acetyl-tetrachlorobenzoic acid³ by the method¹; ferrous ammonium sulphate, sodium carbonate, sodium bicarbonate, sulphuric acid, and sodium hydroxide (AnalaR, B.D.H. grade); *N*-phenyl-anthranilic acid (B.D.H. grade); ether solvent (Alembic); and Ceric sulphate (Technical B.D.H. grade).

Apparatus used : Micropipettes and microburettes used had least count = 0.01 ml; hot plate with a regulator for heat control.

Standard solution of the dye was prepared by dissolving an exactly weighed sample in 1% NaOH solution.

Standard ferrous ammonium sulphate solution was prepared by dissolving an exactly weighed amount in 0.01N H₂SO₄ solution.

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